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Internal Market Orientation and Its Impact on Social and Business Purpose Fulfilment in Organisations

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ABSTRACT

The present study examines the Internal Market Orientation (IMO) concept and its impact on corporate social and business purpose fulfillment. Recognizing employees as pivotal assets, businesses increasingly integrate IMO into their Human Resource Management (HRM) strategies. In this vein, this study positions IMO as a complex internal marketing concept influencing job satisfaction and, subsequently, fulfilling both corporate social and business purposes. To achieve the posed aim, this research employs an empirical quantitative approach and causal study by developing an original theoretical framework, positing seven research hypotheses and surveying 405 employees in business organizations operating in Eastern Europe with an application of the recognized PLS-SEM technique for model validation and hypothesis testing. The findings stemming from this study corroborate the positive effects of IMO implementation on fulfilling an organization's corporate and business purposes. However, this study has not evinced a positive impact of the corporate social purpose fulfillment on accomplishing the organization's business purpose. These and other findings revealed by the present research have significant implications for marketing, HRM, and strategic management literature. On top of that, this research generates valuable insights and recommendations for managers aiming to align HRM strategies with social and business purposes through deploying the IMO concept in their organizations.

1 | Introduction

For a considerable time, businesses have recognised the critical role of employees in achieving organisational goals, understanding that they are not just resources but valuable assets (Mirvis 2012; Morokane et al. 2016). Such a strategic locus of employees in organisations underpins the importance of employer brand appeal in the labour market, effective human resource management (HRM), and workforce retention (George 2015). Recently, businesses have increasingly acknowledged the importance of the inculturation of the internal market orientation (IMO) concept in HRM alongside its other advanced practices (Gounaris et al. 2010; Kazakov et al. 2021). The IMO concept is defined in the marketing literature as “the generation of intelligence relating to employees' needs and wants, dissemination

of this intelligence across departments, and the organisation's responsiveness to it” (Lings 2004, 410). IMO extends the core principles of [external] market orientation, conceptualised initially in Kohli and Jaworski (1990) and Narver and Slater (1990), making them intrinsic to the organisational context. It regards employees as internal customers and seeks to establish a supportive organisational climate that improves engagement, satisfaction, and performance.

By treating employees as internal customers, IMO fosters an employee-centric corporate culture (Boukis et al. 2017). Its goal is to create a positive internal working environment that improves employee engagement with the company and its activities (Ruizalba et al. 2014; González-Porrás et al. 2021). Researchers have identified three primary drivers steering

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IMO implementation in companies, namely, working environment intelligence, internal communications, and management strategies (Lings 2004; S. P. Gounaris 2006). Marketing literature asserts that IMO significantly improves job satisfaction, subsequently boosting employee productivity and performance (Rodrigues and Pinho 2012). This positive impact is crucial for achieving core business purposes (Romi et al. 2018).

Business purpose is defined as the intrinsic reason for an organisation's existence and its mission (Gartenberg et al. 2019; Rodrich-Portugal et al. 2023). It typically includes profit generation and broader ethical, sustainable, and societal goals (Morrison and Mota 2021; Zubeltzu-Jaka et al. 2024). Two primary research streams have explored the purpose of business organisations: one focuses on target-oriented firms' mission with specific financial and non-financial goals (Gartenberg et al. 2019; George et al. 2023), while the other emphasizes a prosocial approach, highlighting responsibility (Jasinenko and Steuber 2023).

A critical research issue is identifying the drivers of business purpose implementation that reside in two dimensions: organization and employees. Organization-wise, researchers have highlighted several factors, including corporate culture (Hong et al. 2021), brand equity (Rahman et al. 2019), resilience and sustainability (Edgeman 2015), technology and innovation (Huang et al. 2021), and market dynamics and customer relationships (Luo and Bhattacharya 2006). For the latter, employee engagement is particularly pivotal for fulfilling business purposes (Sarvaiya et al. 2018). Also, concerning the employee perspective, extant studies emphasize aligning their individual targets with the business purpose (Berg 2015), fostering a positive work environment and job satisfaction (Bakotić 2016), and prioritizing talent acquisition and development (Serenko et al. 2023).

While extensive research has established the importance of employees in implementing social and business purposes, it has often focused on isolated factors without providing a holistic view. Until most recently, most themed studies in the relevant research stream have examined IMO interplay with job satisfaction, brand commitment, and business performance, but researchers have scarcely documented IMO linkages with broader organisational purpose fulfillment and its outcomes. This gap in research highlights the need for a comprehensive conceptual framework that integrates known and emerging drivers relevant to employees. Additionally, prior literature has not adequately aligned target-oriented and responsibility-based purposes as outcomes of IMO implementation. Although marketing literature acknowledges IMO's significance, a notable gap exists in understanding its specific impact on fulfilling social and business purposes. Addressing this gap is crucial for organisations seeking to optimize their HRM strategies to improve business performance and ensure positive societal implications for employees, stakeholders, and society. Our study challenges this gap by linking IMO practices with dual-purpose fulfillment (social and business) through employee perceptions, a priorly underexplored yet critical organisational mechanism.

Organisations operate under growing pressure from governments and society to balance their social responsibilities with

business goals. This has generated an intricate environment where organisational performance and employee satisfaction are closely interlinked (Aguinis and Glavas 2019). The literature is still unclear, though, on how advanced concepts like IMO, if implemented in the organisation, can support this alignment, especially when viewed from the viewpoint of the employees who are the most impacted by the challenges of the present day, according to Krause and Dorsemagen (2024).

Although the IMO concept has been studied predominantly in Western and Asia-Pacific contexts, its enactment in organisations located in Eastern European countries calls for special consideration due to their distinct institutional, historical, and socio-cultural factors. Most Eastern European economies are permeated by transitional institutional environments shaped by post-socialist legacies, hybrid governance models, and evolving labour markets (Mitze and Breidenbach 2024; Kant 2025). These contextual elements influence how firms internalise strategic practices like IMO and how employees perceive organisational purpose. This region's hierarchical managerial cultures, varying degrees of employee voice, and state-influenced business objectives can affect how IMO generates job satisfaction and drives the organisation's business and social purpose fulfilment. Accordingly, scrutinising IMO within this underexplored regional setting augments theoretical understanding and improves the external validity of the IMO concept.

With all that said, a critical question is still unresolved despite the abundance of research on IMO, as follows:

RQ1. *How does IMO implementation influence the fulfillment of a firm's social and business purposes through the lens of employee perceptions?*

By addressing this question, this study responds to the sonorous buzz in the marketing and HR management literature for more sophisticated approaches that examine how internal organisational activities, strategies, and policies influence broader organization's purpose-related outcomes, beyond solely organisational and financial performance metrics. While previous research has explored the impact of IMO on consequences such as satisfaction, productivity, and job performance (see, for example, Ruizalba et al. 2014; Yu et al. 2019; Kazakov et al. 2021), there is a paucity of studies that have examined its forthright role in fostering the simultaneous fulfilment of an organisation's business and social purposes. Bridging this gap is particularly timely due to increasing pressure for organisations to align internal culture with external impact from the implications of COVID-19, ongoing technological disruption, increasingly sophisticated operational environments, such as omnichannel ecosystems (Cuesta-Valiño, Alonso-García, et al. 2024), and rising global economic uncertainty driven by trade tensions and protectionist policies.

Consequently, the purpose of this study is to determine and gauge the impact of IMO implementation on fulfilling social and business purposes by analyzing these relationships from the perspective of employee perceptions. In this line, the objectives of this study are threefold, namely, (1) to identify and validate the key antecedents which steer IMO implementation in organizations; (2) to examine the direct and indirect effects

of IMO implementation on employee job satisfaction, as well as on the fulfillment of social and business purposes; and (3) to explore the theoretical and managerial implications of linking IMO practices with dual-purpose fulfillment in business organizations operating in Eastern Europe. To meet these posed objectives, the present research leverages a rich constellation of theories to explore the reciprocal relationship between employees and organizations. Furthermore, in this vein, this research applies a quantitative causal empirical study comprising surveying 405 employees who work for Eastern European business organizations. To handle the obtained survey data, the present study employs a robust PLS-SEM technique for the developed theoretical model verification, testing hypotheses and generating findings.

Although our study presents compelling data and a well-functioning model, we recognize the need to ground our work in a robust theoretical framework. To meet this need, we explore a linkage between the concept developed under this study and several theoretical foundations, including institutional theory, social information processing theory, attention-based view, equity theory, social exchange theory, and signaling theory. The noted theories provide valuable discernments into the mechanisms underlying IMO implementation and its consequences.

Grounded in these theories and empirically supported findings, this study further contributes to marketing and HR management literature through a theoretical framework that integrates the concept of IMO with social and business purpose fulfillment. With this study, we provide a vision for researchers and practitioners on linkages between IMO implementation and business and social purpose fulfillment, explored through employee perceptions. By empirically confirming the presence of such linkages, our study offers a novel theoretical contribution that expands the scope of IMO research in the marketing and HR management literature. This research not only fills a critical gap in the literature, as previously discussed, but also provides actionable strategies for developing employee engagement and achieving sustainable organizational outcomes.

2 | Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1 | IMO and Its Antecedents

The notion of IMO replicates the basic principles of the market orientation framework (Narver and Slater 1990), adopting this established concept to the organisation's internal environment by focusing on its employees (Lings and Greenley 2010). IMO implies the inculcation of a marketing-savvy approach and customer-centric mindset in managing the company's personnel, treating every employee as a unique individual by knowing and understanding their needs, demands, and expectations (Yu et al. 2019). By implementing IMO in the organisational context, managers execute internal business processes, HRM strategies, and practices to ensure employee satisfaction with their workplace (Kazakov et al. 2021).

According to marketing literature, IMO stands on three pillars representing its antecedents. As previously noted, they

include working environment intelligence (INT), interior communications (COM), and management strategies (STR) (S. P. Gounaris 2006). INT is attributed to the first phase of IMO implementation. It implies intelligence collection to gain knowledge of the external labor market conditions and to ensure that the organization's HRM policies comply with the market conditions (Gounaris et al. 2010; Ruizalba et al. 2014). Moreover, INT scopes an examination of the internal working environment, seeking insights from employees about the various facets of carrying out their jobs, relationships with supervisors, managers, and fellow employees, career perspectives, and sufficiency of support from T&D (Boukis et al. 2017; González-Porras et al. 2021).

The execution of the INT helps organisations ensure that their HRM strategies, practices, and overall working conditions align with labour market specifics and employees' expectations (Lings and Greenley 2010). This process mirrors the tenets of institutional theory (DiMaggio and Powell 1983), according to which firms tend to adapt to external challenges, expectations, and norms, including those of internal stakeholders and employees, to maintain legitimacy and operational effectiveness. Effective communication of policies relevant to the INT construct of IMO ensures that employees can contribute to IMO activities by sharing their opinions, attitudes, and workplace evaluations.

Furthermore, according to the social information processing theory of Salancik and Pfeffer (1978), communication quality is pivotal for shaping employees' perceptions, attitudes, and evaluations of their work environment. In the context of this study, effective INT implies strengthening IMO implementation. On top of that, clear and precise internal communication helps collect accurate and comprehensive data from employees. Hence, INT is significant for organisations as it helps engender employees' support and engagement with IMO initiatives. In this vein, we assert that:

H1. *Efficient working environment intelligence improves IMO implementation in the organisation.*

Marketing literature highlights COM as an IMO element encompassing key activities that commonly comprise communicating employees' company policies and announcements, managers' responses to queries and employee evaluations, as well as interdepartmental sharing of various intelligence data required for job execution (Ruizalba et al. 2014). Moreover, multiple researchers underpin COM's role in employee engagement generated by the organised corporate events, employee entertainment, incentive meetings and gamification that all together shape COM as a significant component of IMO (Martin and To 2013). Furthermore, COM are critical in conveying organisational strategies and policies to employees (Men 2014). By effectively communicating these strategies, organisations can align employees' understanding and behaviours with the planned IMO activities and practices, thus shaping the IMO implementation as a whole. This clear communication is paramount for ensuring employees support and engage with IMO initiatives. Therefore, we hypothesise that:

H2. *Effective interior communications positively influence the execution of IMO within the organisation.*

The next IMO facet focuses on STR, which is integral to the third component of the IMO mix. In crafting these strategies, organisations must take into account the findings received from INT analysis and ensure an alignment with social and business purposes (Tortosa Edo et al. 2015). STR in the domain of IMO stand close to HR functions as they commonly scope employer brand management, talent seeking and acquisition, induction, T&D, and the implementation of effective reward systems, supported by top management commitment and sufficient funding for successful execution (Boukis 2019).

The successful implementation of STR also requires precise and clear communication, which can entail employee acceptance. Suppose managers achieve success in communicating the details and purposes of these strategies through transparency and unambiguity. In that case, they can reach the vantage point where employees understand and support IMO initiatives, implying their more effective implementation in the organization. Such an inference supports Spence (1973). According to this framework, communication is deemed a signal of managerial intent. Its clarity and fairness denote drivers of employee trust and engagement in organizational initiatives. Therefore, communication transparency helps align employee actions with organizational goals. Standing on these grounds, we pose the following hypothesis:

H3. *An effective implementation of management strategies generates positive effects on IMO implementation in the organisation.*

2.2 | Job Satisfaction as a Consequence of IMO Implementation

According to the accumulated research, employees' satisfaction with their jobs is paramount for generating organisational efficiency, improving business performance, and fulfilling social and business purposes (Koekemoer et al. 2020; Cuesta-Valiño et al. 2021). More specifically, the literature indicates job satisfaction effects on improvement in employee productivity, loyalty to the organisation, and image of the employer brand, simultaneously reducing personnel turnovers and talent acquisition costs (Tortosa et al. 2009; Gutiérrez Rodríguez et al. 2017). On top of that, prior research has established job satisfaction as the direct consequence of implementing the IMO concept in the organisation (S. Gounaris 2008). Job satisfaction will likely improve when employees perceive that organisational strategies are well-communicated (Bernroider 2007) and aligned with their needs at the workplace, which implies that IMO is enacted (Ruizalba et al. 2014). Effective communication during IMO implementation ensures employees feel valued and understand IMO's significance for them, increasing their satisfaction. This perception is critical for achieving higher job satisfaction levels (Boukis and Kabadayi 2020).

As we previously noted, IMO is paramount in shaping employee perceptions and attitudes towards their working environment, which is intrinsic to the employing organisation. According to the social exchange theory (SET), employees develop reciprocal relationships with their employers based on perceived support and fairness (Blau 1964). In the domain of IMO, an appropriate implementation of its practices makes employees believe that

the organisation cares for them and values their contributions to business performance. The reciprocal relationship between the organisation and employees, executed through managers, significantly improves job satisfaction, as employees feel supported in their roles, according to Cropanzano and Mitchell (2005).

Additionally, equity theory (Adams 1965) reinforces that employee satisfaction will likely increase if they perceive or feel fairness and respectful recognition in organizational treatment. These noted outcomes in the vein of the equity theory are closely linked to the effective implementation of IMO practices. Research has shown that perceived organizational support from implementing responsive strategies, as an outcome of carrying out IMO, is firmly linked to increased job satisfaction (Rhoades and Eisenberger 2002). Thereby, we posit the following hypothesis for testing under this research:

H4. *IMO implementation in the organisation positively influences employees' job satisfaction.*

2.3 | Linkage Between Job Satisfaction and Social Purpose Fulfilment

The effects of job satisfaction on the fulfilment of social purpose, focused on employees, stakeholders, and society, have received some degree of consideration from academia, advancing social purpose to understanding it as a more holistic perspective (Cuesta-Valiño et al. 2019; Story and Castanheira 2019; Abdelhakim and Agwa 2022). Several studies evince that job satisfaction positively impacts social purpose fulfilment and, subsequently, its organisational performance in achieving the goals of the organisation's socially-centric strategies (Luo and Bhattacharya 2006; Islam et al. 2021). Furthermore, according to prior studies, job satisfaction engenders social organisational commitment, which mediates the relationship between job satisfaction and employees' behaviour as citizens (Feather and Rauter 2004; Lumley et al. 2011; Nurjanah et al. 2020).

Interestingly, researchers have mostly tended to zoom in on the linkage between job satisfaction, employee loyalty, and social purpose fulfilment through the lens of corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Cuesta-Valiño et al. 2021). In this line, prior studies tend to circumvent, consciously or unconsciously, the concept of social purpose, which is noted less in the literature. Although researchers argue that CSR implies organizational commitment and social purpose is more relevant to the organizational goal and activity to achieve it (Bansal and Song 2017; Levillain and Segrestin 2019), these two concepts are closely related. Thus, CSR-relevant literature can be scoped as a research background for this study.

Furthermore, extant research focuses mainly on the growing body of evidence of increased job satisfaction following the employees' perception of taking part in fulfilling the social purpose or CSR (Noh 2021). The employees' awareness of their participation in such fulfillment makes them consider that their work is more meaningful for society and the environment. Such perception of a job's social sense and meaning implies that HRM or IMO-related factors do not exclusively shape job satisfaction. This proposition is again grounded in SET (Blau 1964) as it

suggests in this study's settings that employees' perception of the support and the value received from the organization will more likely drive them to engage in prosocial organizational behaviors, including efforts aligned with the social purpose (Organ and Ryan 1995). According to prior literature, it can be improved when an employee realizes their contribution to societal well-being (Camilleri 2022). However, when job satisfaction drives employee willingness to contribute to fulfilling social purpose, the reverse link remains poorly documented in the extant literature.

Nonetheless, another research stream in the field argues that job satisfaction generated by job-related factors such as remuneration, relationships with supervisors, and career perspectives should be ensured before improving it further based on employee engagement in fulfilling the social purpose (Koekemoer et al. 2020). We agree with these researchers and advance their approach by featuring the IMO concept as a marketing-savvy approach necessary to generate job satisfaction from job-related factors. On top of it, clear communication of the organisation's social goals and how employees' roles contribute to these goals can strengthen this relationship. This alignment ensures that employees' efforts are directed toward achieving the social purpose.

As priorly indicated, SET explains job satisfaction impacts individual employee outcomes, but this theory extends to broader organisational domains such as social purpose fulfilment. Thanks to SET concepts such as costs, rewards, and comparison levels of alternatives, satisfied employees are more likely to engage in discretionary behaviours that support the organisation's social objectives (Organ and Ryan 1995). SET suggests that valued employees are more likely to reciprocate with behaviours that align with organisational goals, including those related to social responsibility (Cropanzano and Mitchell 2005). Research indicates that job satisfaction predicts employee engagement in CSR activities (Aguinis and Glavas 2019).

In line with the above, our research posits and tests the following hypothesis, which is critical for understanding the impact of job satisfaction on social purpose fulfillment:

H5. *Job satisfaction has a positive influence on social purpose fulfillment.*

2.4 | Exploring the Interconnections Between Job Satisfaction and Business Purpose Fulfilment

The extant literature addresses the linkage between job satisfaction and business purpose fulfillment. It establishes another effect of job satisfaction, indicating that it positively influences business performance and, thus, the fulfillment of the business purpose (Gartenberg et al. 2019). Satisfied employees are motivated to perform better in their positions. They are also more committed to achieving the organization's business goals, thus fulfilling the organization's business purpose (Ahmad and Raja 2021).

Job satisfaction boosts employees' motivation and performance, directly contributing to the firm's business goals. Blau (1964)

explains this linkage through perceived organisational support and fairness, which increase employees' discretionary effort toward business goals (Eisenberger et al. 1986). Simultaneously, receiving communications relevant to business goals, strategies, and, more importantly, financial and marketing performance results helps employees recognize their contributions better (Kalogiannidis 2020). It can reinforce job satisfaction, which is grounded in the knowledge of the positive outcomes of the completed job. Sequentially, our research should also examine the influence of job satisfaction on business purpose fulfillment. It is a pivotal facet to consider, as job satisfaction has been noted to influence business performance, according to previous research (Chi and Gursoy 2009).

Moreover, SET can also explain the contribution of satisfied employees to fulfilling the organisation's business purposes. According to SET, employees who perceive high organisational support and fairness are more committed and motivated to perform better at their workplace. Increased motivation and commitment translate into improved productivity, reduced turnover, and improved business performance (Eisenberger et al. 1986). Researchers observed a positive relationship between job satisfaction and various measures of business performance, including profitability and market success (Judge et al. 2001). Moreover, in accord with the tenets of the signalling theory (Spence 1973), if managers communicate fair and transparent feedback to employees concerning their job performance, the latter are more likely to perceive their work as meaningful and essential, thus reinforcing business purpose fulfilment further. Therefore, we posit that:

H6. *Job satisfaction has a positive influence on a firm's fulfillment of its business purpose.*

2.5 | Social Purpose Implementation Effect on Business Purpose Fulfilment

On top of that, striving for sustainable and socially responsible practices makes it possible to make an organisation adequate for its social purpose (Belas et al. 2021). Sequentially, acknowledging the complex relationship between job satisfaction and social purpose fulfilment becomes crucial for creating a harmonious and purpose-driven workplace. Simultaneously, several researchers have argued that it is essential to ensure that implementing social purpose advances the organisation's overarching business purpose (Weller 2017). Clear communication of the social purpose and its alignment with the business purpose ensures that employees understand the interconnectedness of these goals (Lim and Greenwood 2017). This understanding fosters a cohesive effort towards fulfilling social and business objectives, increasing the overall firm's performance.

Organisations that actively pursue their social purpose often see improvements in their business performance. Based on its principle of reciprocity, SET provides a perspective through which it is possible to apprehend this relationship. Organisations engaging in socially responsible practices foster an encouraging working climate that develops participating employees' self-esteem, which positively influences their loyalty and commitment (Cropanzano and Mitchell 2005). It can be further explained

through the lens of SET and ABV, as prosocial organisational climate indicates consideration for employee values (Ocasio 1997). Sequentially, such an internal climate motivates employee commitment and focus on organisational priorities. This favourable climate, in turn, leads to better business outcomes as employees are more motivated to support organisational goals (Turban and Greening 1997). Research has demonstrated that firms with vital CSR programs tend to perform better financially (Orlitzky et al. 2003). With that being said, this research poses the last research hypothesis:

H7. *Implementing the social purpose improves a firm's business purpose fulfilment.*

2.6 | Summary of Theoretical Foundations and Conceptual Framework

The theoretical framework developed under this study relies on a mix of theories recognized in organizational and marketing research. Each employed theory underpins specific relevant constructs and relationships within the estimated conceptual model. In this vein, the institutional theory of DiMaggio and Powell (1983) supports the design of IMO antecedents, particularly working environment intelligence, explaining how organizations adopt internal practices in response to institutional expectations for legitimacy and employee responsiveness. Thus, institutional theory further bolsters the conventional IMO concept that originated in Lings (2004) and was later ameliorated in S. Gounaris (2008).

Next, social information processing theory (Salancik and Pfeffer 1978) supports communication as a mechanism through which employees interpret organisational intent, policies, and culture, which is critical for effective IMO implementation in the organisation. Our suggested model also leans on signalling theory (Spence 1973), which explains how strategic communication of management practices, social and business purposes, shapes employee attitudes by diminishing ambiguity and thus

building trust. SET (Blau 1964; Cropanzano and Mitchell 2005) and equity theory (Adams 1965) offer the conceptual backbone for understanding how perceived support, fairness, and reciprocity drive job satisfaction and subsequent behaviors contributing to social and business outcomes.

Finally, the Attention-Based View (Ocasio 1997) provides insight into how organizational and employee attention is directed toward meaningful goals, highlighting how attention to social initiatives can drive broader strategic alignment. These theoretical pillars collectively justify the relationships tested in our model and provide conceptual rigor to each of the hypotheses developed in this study. Figure 1 below depicts the conceptual framework developed following the literature review, consideration of relevant theories, and the set of posed hypotheses.

3 | Materials and Methods

3.1 | Questionnaire Development

As this research employed a survey methodology, we developed a questionnaire for data collection. The questionnaire form included five questions relevant to descriptive statistics to categorize the derived sample and 21 questions pertaining to indicators whose values were necessary to run the estimated model developed under this study (Figure 1). Descriptive category questions comprised study participants' age, gender, job, position, number of employees in the organization, its approximate turnover in euros, targeted type of customers (B2B, B2C), and sector or industry where the organization operates. We relied on the previously empirically tested measurements for questions where indicators are measured. We adopted relevant scales from the extant literature to generate these questions and favored a Likert scale with increments of 1–7 to accommodate comfort in responding while surveying.

Researchers have noted that a 7-point Likert scale provides more response options to the survey participants and, consequently,

FIGURE 1 | Theoretical model.

is more reliable and capable of capturing more precise responses, offering greater sensitivity than a 5-point Likert scale (Finstad 2010; Kusmaryono et al. 2022). Moreover, extant literature indicates that a 7-point scale will likely diminish central tendency bias. Hence, it improves the precision of responses, thereby improving the questionnaire's psychometric abilities (Leung 2011).

In this vein, this study has employed nine scales linked with working environment intelligence, internal communications, and management strategies/implementation from S. P. Gounaris (2006); three scales relevant to IMO adapted from Lings and Greenley (2010) and Ruizalba et al. (2014); three scales to measure job satisfaction incorporated from Hartline and Ferrell (1996); three scales taken and modified from Islam et al. (2021) to gauge social purpose fulfillment grounded in study participants' perception of their employer's degree of compliance with CSR. Finally, we consolidated and acculturated the three remaining scales to evaluate business purpose fulfillment from Yu et al. (2019) and Papadas et al. (2019).

Under this study, the data was collected in a non-English speaking country, and a professional agency was contracted for questionnaire translation, which another third-party translation services provider has further verified. Next, we executed a questionnaire validation process to ascertain the integrity of the developed survey form and guarantee the clarity and comprehension of the questions. Using the Delphi technique, we communicated with five university professors from departments specializing in marketing and human resources studies to receive insights and suggestions for questionnaire improvement. Moreover, the research team met with two marketing managers and three HR managers for the same purposes. These activities aimed to identify any potential inconsistencies and refine the phrasing of the questions where needed.

3.2 | Sampling Technique and Data Collection

The current study received assistance from the local association of HR managers, who supported the research initiative and shared their membership database with the research team. In this situation, a convenience sampling approach (Jager et al. 2017) was deemed the most appropriate for collecting reliable data for our study. Capitalizing on the contact data source received from the association, we distributed 2000 letters to HR managers asking them to share a link for an online survey among employees in their respective organizations. The data collection process lasted almost 60 days in the last quarter of 2022. To ensure the even distribution of employing organizations in the research sample, we aimed to receive three filled-in forms from each company surveyed by questionnaire distribution. Our approach to HR managers directly helped attain 423 completely filled-in questionnaire forms, which also comply with the condition of even distribution noted above. During the data engineering process, 18 forms were discarded due to technical errors, resulting in a sample of $n = 405$, representing 131 companies. Obtaining the indicated number of completed forms implies an overall 26% response rate, which meets the acceptable threshold, according to Menon et al. (1996).

The collected data were first examined with exploratory data analysis to comprehend the characteristics of the resulting sample. Table 1 below depicts the sample properties obtained following the data collection process.

3.3 | Common Bias Method and Nested Data Issues

We employed procedural and statistical remedies to address potential common method bias. Procedurally, we ensured respondent anonymity and constructed a clear and concise questionnaire, heeding suggestions in MacKenzie and Podsakoff (2012). Then, we verified questionnaire consistency and translation as indicated in §3.1.

Statistically, Harman's single-factor test revealed that no single factor accounted for most of the variance (Sums of Squared % of Variance = 37.24), suggesting that common method bias is not a significant problem for the outcomes of this research (Podsakoff and Organ 1986). Additionally, we included a marker variable while running our model and found no significant correlations with the model constructs, further indicating that standard method variance is not an issue in our data (Lindell and Whitney 2001; Podsakoff et al. 2003).

In addition, this study employed a mixed multilevel modelling analysis technique (Hofmann and Gavin 1998) to rule out possible issues with nested data, as it was collected from 405 employees representing 131 companies. Its outcomes indicate no significant problems with the nesting of data. The Intraclass Correlation Coefficient (ICC) has a value of 0.023, suggesting minimal clustering effects. The computed random effects components variance showed a small company-level residual effect variance (0.24) relative to the employee-level random effect variance (0.02), further supporting the lack of significant nesting effects. All fixed effects for key predictors were statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Therefore, the nesting of data does not significantly affect the findings of our study, which will be delineated in the next section.

4 | Results

4.1 | Model Convergent and Discriminant Validity Verification

In this research, we favored established PLS-SEM over the covariance-based CB-SEM approach due to its better suitability for social studies. Researchers note the benefits of the PLS-SEM approach in estimating structural factor-based models and analyzing paths between model constructs compared to the CB-SEM technique. These benefits comprise more lenient requirements for the data sample size and mean distribution (Astrachan et al. 2014). Also, literature acknowledges that indicators in the PLS-SEM model generally receive higher loading values following the model estimation, deliver better construct reliability and validity test results, and do not require a wide array of fit indices needed in the CB-SEM method application (Dash and Paul 2021).

TABLE 1 | Sample descriptive statistics.

		Frequency, employees	Frequency, companies	Valid percent	IMO mean	Standard deviation
Gender	Female	216	70	53.333	3.861	1.905
	Male	189	61	46.667	3.418	1.880
Number of employees	1	19	6	4.691	5.403	1.028
	11 up to 50	132	43	32.593	3.198	1.746
	2 up to 10	162	53	40.000	4.050	1.893
	More than 50	85	28	20.988	3.296	1.926
	No answer	7	2	1.728		
Approximate annual turnover	Up to €2 million	192	62	46.200	3.804	1.886
	Up to €10 million	78	25	19.259	3.238	1.762
	Up to €43 million	35	11	8.642	3.410	2.097
	More than €43 million	16	5	3.800	3.657	1.834
	No answer	84	27	20.200		
Targeted type of customers	Both ultimate consumers and businesses (B2B2C)	67	22	16.543	3.346	1.931
	Government organizations (B2G)	43	14	10.617	3.166	1.843
	Other businesses (B2B)	180	58	44.444	3.889	1.923
	Ultimate consumers (B2C)	102	33	25.185	3.574	1.867
	No answer	13	4	3.210		
Business sector	Cleaning services	6	2	1.481	2.168	0.753
	Consumer services	31	10	7.654	3.828	2.041
	Corporate services	118	38	29.136	3.638	1.884
	IT services	13	4	3.210	4.717	1.762
	Manufacturing and craftworks	60	19	14.815	3.881	1.936
	Restaurants and catering	18	6	4.444	2.833	1.908
	Retail business	59	19	14.568	3.517	1.838
	Transportation services	14	5	3.457	2.119	1.067
	Wholesale business	72	23	17.778	4.019	1.934
	No answer	14	5	3.457		

To estimate the developed model (Figure 1), this research has utilized the SmartPLS software application to run the PLS-SEM algorithm for CFA execution with the settings including a maximum iteration number of 6000 and initial weights of 1. Next to the first model estimation step, we applied bootstrapping to carry out model path analysis essential for testing the seven posed hypotheses. The bootstrapping procedure algorithm was set to percentile bootstrap, parallel processing, generating 5000 samples, fixed seed, and a significance level of 0.05. The graphical output of the above-elucidated bootstrapping procedure implementation is depicted in Figure 2. The values indicated inside

the latent construct represent their respective Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values.

Table 2 exhibits the results of CFA implementation and draws indicator names with their respective factor loading values, all of which are statistically significant (Table 2).

Next, in Table 3, we illustrate the results of running the standard PLS CFA algorithm concerning the evaluation of the reliability and measurement model convergent validity of the utilised indicator scales. The outputs of model reliability and convergent

FIGURE 2 | Bootstrap procedure application output on measurement and structural model.

validity reveal no evidence of issues related to convergent validity within the estimated measurement model, as further detailed in Table 3.

Similar to the model convergent validity tests, the evaluation of discriminant validity has yet to show problems with it, as all heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlations (HTMT) have values below 0.9 (Franke and Sarstedt 2019). Table 4 below exhibits the outcomes of the estimated model's discriminant validity verification.

In addition, estimated model fit indices of SRMR=0.079, $\chi^2=1407.331$, and NFI=0.828 also revealed the values positioned in the acceptable thresholds (Schuberth et al. 2023). Moreover, we implemented the Gaussian Copula (GC) approach to rule out possible endogeneity issues (Becker et al. 2022). Based on the above-noted model fit parameters and output values of GC (INT_{GC} ⇒ IMO: 0.181; COM_{GC} ⇒ IMO: 0.351; STR_{GC} ⇒ IMO: 0.176; IMO_{GC} ⇒ SAT: 0.422; SAT_{GC} ⇒ SPU: 0.377; SAT_{GC} ⇒ BPU: 0.267; SPU_{GC} ⇒ BPU: 0.343), where $p < 0.05$ for all GC values, we conclude that the GC variable significantly explains part of the variance in the dependent variable and thus endogeneity issues are not present in the estimated model.

By accumulating the above-noted results, this research affirms that the estimated measurement and structural model meet the criteria for scale reliability and the convergent and discriminant validity of model latent constructs, making it eligible for hypothesis testing, which we illustrate further in this section.

4.2 | Path Analysis and Hypothesis Tests

A priorly delineated bootstrapping procedure also facilitated the SEM path analysis implementation necessary to test the research hypotheses posed under this study. In Table 5, we reveal the outcomes stemming from the path analysis execution.

Research hypotheses testing has confirmed that activities in the domain of Working environment intelligence, Interior Communications, and Management strategies are essential conditions to precipitate IMO implementation in organisations because the relevant hypotheses of H1 (sample mean: $\beta_{INT \Rightarrow IMO} = 0.183$, $p \text{ value}_{INT \Rightarrow IMO} = 0.001$), H2 (sample mean: $\beta_{COM \Rightarrow IMO} = 0.507$, $p \text{ value}_{COM \Rightarrow IMO} = 0.000$), H3 (sample mean: $\beta_{STR \Rightarrow IMO} = 0.171$, $p \text{ value}_{STR \Rightarrow IMO} = 0.004$) cannot be rejected. Sequentially, IMO generates a positive effect on employee job satisfaction according to our findings, as H4 (sample mean: $\beta_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT} = 0.574$, $p \text{ value}_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT} = 0.000$) is accepted. Furthermore, path analysis evinces positive employee job satisfaction impact on the social and business purposes fulfilment as H5 (sample mean: $\beta_{SAT \Rightarrow SPU} = 0.716$, $p \text{ value}_{SAT \Rightarrow SPU} = 0.000$) and H6 (sample mean: $\beta_{SAT \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.258$, $p \text{ value}_{SAT \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.001$) are not rejected as well. Conversely, the attained results indicate the impossibility of H6 acceptance (sample mean: $\beta_{SPU \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.129$, $p \text{ value}_{SPU \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.062$), implying that social business purpose fulfilment does not necessarily predispose the accomplishment of the organisation's business purpose.

4.3 | IMO Specific Indirect and Total Indirect Effects on the Social and Business Purpose Fulfilment

The complexity of the validated model (Figure 2) determines the presence of multifaceted indirect effects between latent constructs in the theoretical framework. To determine the full impact of IMO implementation on social and business purpose fulfilment, the present study has addressed its posed overarching research question by supplementing the primary path analysis and hypotheses verification by evaluating specific indirect and total indirect effects in the validated model. In Table 6, we delineate the IMO-driven specific indirect effects on social and business purpose fulfilment, which is mediated mainly by employee satisfaction and, in this case, also by social purpose fulfilment.

TABLE 2 | Scales indicator factor loadings.

Construct	Indicator	Scale	Adapted from	Values	Factor loading	p
INT	int1	Supervisors meet face to face with employees to understand better their needs	S. P. Gounaris (2006)	1-7	0.917	0.000
	int2	Employees classification into well-defined groups according to their individual needs				
	int3	Organisation continuously monitors remuneration packages and fringe benefits offered by organisations in he external labour market				
COM	com1	Supervisors are always available to meet personally with an employee if such a meeting is requested	S. P. Gounaris (2006)	1-7	0.862	0.000
	com2	Employees are aware of what is going on in the organisation				
	com3	Corporate events (parties, team building workshops) are beneficial for the company and valued by employees				
STR	str1	Supervisors are clearly geared toward solving any problems that employees may have and providing them with the support they need to perform their job well	S. P. Gounaris (2006)	1-7	0.916	0.000
	str2	The company systematically and continuously organises training seminars so that employees can develop their skills				
	str3	Remuneration raise and career advancement is grounded on regular employee evaluation with the help of KPIs				
IMO	imo1	Managers know and understand internal working environment and external labour market conditions	Lings and Greenley (2010); Ruizalba et al. (2014)	1-7	0.955	0.000
	imo2	The communication system in this organisation is effective				
	imo3	Managers plan and implement employee-centric HRM strategies successfully.				
SAT	sat1	Employee perceived satisfaction with the relationship with his/her respective supervisors	Hartline and Ferrell (1996)	1-7	0.847	0.000
	sat2	Employee perceived satisfaction with the support received from the organisation				
	sat3	Employee perceived satisfaction with the career opportunities I have in this company				

(Continues)

TABLE 2 | (Continued)

Construct	Indicator	Scale	Adapted from	Values	Factor loading	p
SPU	spu1	This company works for the sake of sustainable society	Islam et al. (2021)	1-7	0.931	0.000
	spu2	This organisation is socially oriented towards its employees, stakeholders and society		1-7	0.964	0.000
	spu3	This organisation executes ethical business		1-7	0.955	0.000
BPU	bpu1	Customers are satisfied with the product/service delivered by organisation and are loyal to its brand	Yu et al. (2019); Papadas et al. (2019)	1-7	0.894	0.000
	bpu2	This organisation is profitable and wins the competition in the market		1-7	0.930	0.000
	bpu3	Sales and profits of this organisations grow every year		1-7	0.849	0.000

Examining specific indirect effects provides supplementary evidence for the primary research hypotheses' H4–H7 verification results. In this line, according to the model's specific indirect effects analysis, hypotheses H4–H6 receive further confirmation of their acceptance as the effects in chains of $IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow BPU$ (sample mean $\beta_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.146$, p value $_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.002$) and $IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU$ (sample mean $\beta_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU} = 0.411$, p value $_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU} = 0.000$) are statistically significant. Sequentially, rejecting H7 is grounded in the specific indirect effects evaluation of the $IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU \Rightarrow BPU$ chain, which reveals a low regression coefficient value and an insignificant p value (sample mean $\beta_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.053$, p value $_{IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU \Rightarrow BPU} = 0.069$). These results are supported and thereby ultimately confirmed by the total effects of IMO on the firm's social and business purpose fulfilment analysis depicted in Table 7.

In the next section, we discuss the research findings stemming from the above-delineated data analysis.

5 | Discussion and Conclusions

5.1 | Discussion

The accomplishment of this research pursued to contribute to the marketing, HRM, and strategic management literature by delving into the organisation's business purpose fulfillment through the implementation of the IMO concept. The completed study has targeted the establishment of positive IMO effects to achieve the above-noted types of a firm's purpose. The primary aim of the study sought to bridge an extant gap in the research established by scarcely documented drivers of employee engagement in a firm's purpose fulfillment. By reaching the research aim, this research sheds more light on the positive implications of IMO implementation on a firm's purpose fulfillment. Moreover, the findings stemming from the present study may guide managers in their endeavors to fulfill social and business purposes by the inculturation of the IMO concept in their organisations.

These findings also directly address the previously set research objectives. In this vein, first, our study identifies and empirically validates working environment intelligence, interior communications, and management strategies as critical antecedents of IMO implementation in organizations. Second, the present study documents the positive and significant IMO influence on employee job satisfaction, which henceforth drives the fulfillment of both social and business purposes. However, no direct effect from social to business purpose fulfillment was found in our study. Third, this study contributes to the theory domain by integrating several significant theoretical perspectives that explain the observed linkages. In the domain of managerial practice, this research unveils actionable ideas for managers seeking to align their HRM strategies with the fulfillment of broader organizational purposes.

Placidly, our findings assert that the IMO essence is sculpted by three building blocks comprising the organisation's activities in the domains of working environment intelligence, interior communications, and management strategies. In

TABLE 3 | The outputs of the scales reliability and model convergent validity tests.

Construct	Cronbach α	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
INT	0.877	0.888	0.924	0.803
COM	0.853	0.869	0.910	0.772
STR	0.901	0.913	0.938	0.835
SAT	0.806	0.808	0.886	0.721
IMO	0.804	0.915	0.885	0.728
SPU	0.946	0.946	0.965	0.902
BPU	0.872	0.913	0.921	0.795

TABLE 4 | Model discriminant validity test results.

	INT	COM	STR	IMO	SAT	SPU
INT						
COM	0.829					
STR	0.859	0.841				
IMO	0.774	0.881	0.770			
SAT	0.774	0.750	0.661	0.685		
SPU	0.864	0.890	0.847	0.810	0.817	
BPU	0.323	0.392	0.286	0.691	0.405	0.335

this vein, this finding echoes the outcomes of the prior research in the IMO field (S. P. Gounaris 2006). Interestingly, research findings highlight the significance of interior communications in shaping IMO implementation, as this conceptual element outperforms the other two IMO components by having a higher regression coefficient with a value twice as high and effect size (t -values) as high as three times that of working environment intelligence and management strategies planning and execution ($t_{INT \Rightarrow IMO} = 3.298$; $t_{COM \Rightarrow IMO} = 9.260$; $t_{STR \Rightarrow IMO} = 2.875$). This particular finding signals that the organisation's employees distinguish interior communications as an IMO element, which is the most significant for them.

The following research finding reported by this study concerns the linkage between IMO implementation and employee job satisfaction. As the IMO mainstream research in the field has routinely scoped this peculiar issue, commonly establishing job satisfaction as an initial IMO consequence mediating a variety of the second-order repercussions, namely employee productivity, job commitment, loyalty to the organization, organizational and business performance (see, for example, Tortosa et al. 2009; Ruizalba et al. 2014; Yu et al. 2019), we also could not neglect scrutiny of IMO's relationship with job satisfaction. By exploring this relationship, this study adheres to the growing body of evidence of the positive IMO relationship with employees' satisfaction with their jobs and the workplace by empirically asserting the existence of such a statistically significant linkage in the model validated under the present research.

Furthermore, this research has corroborated positive outcomes on the firm's purpose fulfillment generated by IMO-associated employee job satisfaction. This finding implies that when employees attain satisfaction with their workplace, they are more likely to support and contribute to fulfilling the social purpose of their employing organizations. Thus, this research outcome underpins a connection between job satisfaction and an organization's commitment to improving societal well-being, reflected in the endeavors to fulfill a social purpose. Various stakeholders, including employees, are increasingly drawn to organizations that actively engage in social purpose initiatives (Kim et al. 2020), leading to a positive feedback loop where CSR positively influences job satisfaction. In this vein, the noted outcome resonates with the prior studies, which, albeit unlike this study, have addressed and established a converse effect of social purpose fulfillment in the form of CSR on job satisfaction (Abdelhakim and Agwa 2022).

The subsequent finding stemming from the accomplished study reinforces the evidence of the possible positive influence that job satisfaction engenders for the sake of the fulfillment of business purposes. Our research asserts that organizations emphasizing employee satisfaction with their jobs are likely to improve business performance, subsequently achieving financial goals and therefore fulfilling their business purpose. The attained outcome underscores the significance of recognizing the positive effects of job satisfaction on achieving the business purpose. It stresses implementing the IMO concept as a significant factor in employee satisfaction with the workplace. The positive relationship between job satisfaction and business performance, including achieving business goals and fulfilling business purpose, has been indicated in the recent literature, so our research supports prior findings and adheres to the chorus of researchers confirming such a positive connection (Ahmad and Raja 2021).

Conversely, our study has found no evidence of social purpose implementation influence on business purpose fulfillment. This intriguing finding challenges prior studies establishing an affirmative correlation between these two firms' purpose types (Probohudono et al. 2021) while echoing Hamdoun et al. (2021). The latter researchers have determined that social purpose, referred to as CSR in their respective study, has a positive impact on the organization's business performance indicators, such as competitive advantage. Still, simultaneously, it does not directly improve the financial performance of the same organization.

TABLE 5 | Research hypothesis tests.

<i>H_n</i>	Analysed model path	β , original sample	β , sample mean	Standard deviation	<i>t</i> -statistics	<i>p</i>	Accepted?
H1	INT \Rightarrow IMO	0.182	0.183	0.055	3.298	0.001	Yes
H2	COM \Rightarrow IMO	0.507	0.507	0.055	9.260	0.000	Yes
H3	STR \Rightarrow IMO	0.172	0.171	0.060	2.875	0.004	Yes
H4	IMO \Rightarrow SAT	0.573	0.574	0.036	15.890	0.000	Yes
H5	SAT \Rightarrow SPU	0.715	0.716	0.025	28.537	0.000	Yes
H6	SAT \Rightarrow BPU	0.255	0.258	0.075	3.398	0.001	Yes
H7	SPU \Rightarrow BPU	0.130	0.129	0.070	1.865	0.062	No

TABLE 6 | Specific IMO indirect effects analysis.

Specific IMO indirect effects in the model	β , original sample	β , sample mean	Standard deviation	<i>t</i> -statistics	<i>p</i>
IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU \Rightarrow BPU	0.053	0.053	0.029	1.818	0.069
IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow BPU	0.146	0.149	0.046	3.148	0.002
IMO \Rightarrow SAT \Rightarrow SPU	0.410	0.411	0.035	11.566	0.000

TABLE 7 | Total indirect effects analysis.

	β , original sample	β , sample mean	Standard deviation	<i>t</i> -statistics	<i>p</i>
IMO \Rightarrow BPU	0.199	0.202	0.034	5.948	0.000
IMO \Rightarrow SPU	0.410	0.411	0.035	11.557	0.000

The noted controversy can be due to the social purpose peculiarities intrinsic to a specific organization, the specifics of the business sector, the domestic or international market of operation, and the organization's activities' alignment with the social purpose fulfillment for a more precise determination of the outcomes. On top of that, the effects of social fulfillment on business-based purposes may naturally become visible solely in the long term; thus, such evaluation can be a strenuous task.

Finally, by grounding our findings in related theories such as institutional theory, social information processing theory, attention-based view framework, signaling theory, social exchange theory, and equity theory, we provide a robust theoretical foundation that improves our understanding of the means through which IMO may influence employees' perceptions and behaviors. These theoretical stances underscore the significance of clear and transparent communications in implementing IMO, aligning employee actions with organizational goals, improving job satisfaction, and fulfilling the firm's social and business purposes.

5.2 | Theoretical and Managerial Implications

The completed study unveils a tapestry of implications significant for theory and practice. It divulges insightful findings

into the IMO concept and its profound consequences for social and business purpose fulfillment, augmenting the extant corpus of marketing, HRM, and strategic management literature. Concerning theoretical implications, this research first contributes to marketing, Human Resource Management (HRM), and strategic management literature by addressing the conspicuous hiatus in the prior studies. This particular contribution stems from addressing and exploring the determinants of social and business purpose fulfillment from the poorly documented perspective of the employee's role and engagement in this process.

Second, this research confirms and clarifies the affirmative consequences of IMO implementation on social and business purpose fulfillment. Such a discerned positive nexus between IMO implementation, employee job satisfaction, and the firm's purpose fulfillment highlights the indispensable role of IMO in cultivating a contented workforce, thereby ensuring the longevity of the IMO concept's advantages to the organization. Our study asserts the existence of positive IMO influence on social and business purpose fulfillment that arises after its implementation in the organization. In this vein, the research findings indicate that IMO is associated with a cascading impact on fulfilling social and business purposes by improving job satisfaction. Our study shows that positive total and specific indirect IMO effects in this realm are plausible.

Third, our study's findings do not establish a positive impact of social purpose fulfillment on implementing organizational business purposes. This finding, in particular, questions and challenges prevailing conventions found in the prior literature. Such a controversial result augments and feeds the ongoing debate in the literature on the role of the social purpose in business performance improvement and achieving the organization's financial goals, hence accomplishing its business purpose.

On top of that, our research makes significant theoretical contributions by integrating multiple theoretical lenses to explore the impact of IMO on job satisfaction and organizational outcomes. In this domain, by applying institutional theory, we highlight the role of organizational legitimacy in driving IMO practices. Social information processing theory and the attention-based view underscore the importance of communication and attentional processes in shaping employee perceptions. Signaling theory and equity theory emphasize the impact of organizational signals and fair treatment on employee behavior. Next, our study extends the theoretical landscape by applying social exchange theory to explain the mechanisms through which IMO influences job satisfaction and organizational outcomes. These discernments advance our understanding of IMO and provide a comprehensive framework for future research on managerial communication and employee satisfaction with the job. According to Bergh (2003) and Whetten (1989), a robust theoretical contribution involves clarifying the constructs, relationships, and contextual conditions that shape a phenomenon. By doing so, we offer a complete understanding of how IMO practices show a positive relationship with reciprocal benevolent behaviors among employees, thereby linking IMO strategies to broader organizational purposes.

Concerning this study's implications for managers, they will discover that our findings are particularly relevant as they underscore the importance of developing IMO practices that may improve employee-employer relationships. Our study establishes a rationale for managers to implement supportive and fair practices in IMO implementation that increase job satisfaction and may influence the fulfillment of social and business purposes. By doing so, companies can create a harmonious and purpose-driven workplace that aligns with contemporary calls for social responsibility and business excellence. These firm-intrinsic initiatives can benefit and be further advanced through strategic collaborations with governmental and public organizations, as suggested by Gahramanova (2023). Furthermore, the alignment of internal practices with social purpose fulfillment may positively influence positive consumer feedback and attitudes and drive purchase intention, as evinced in several works of Cuesta-Valiño et al. (2022, 2023); Cuesta-Valiño, Gutiérrez-Rodríguez, et al. (2024) in the retail context.

Second, managers can benefit from deploying specific IMO building blocks in their corporate strategies. To comply with Working Environment Intelligence (INT), they should regularly organize employee surveys and meetings to collect attitudes and evaluations about the work environment, job satisfaction, and needs. Also, AI-driven solutions using computer vision technology and in-facility surveillance systems can now detect

employees' emotions and determine the grade of their job satisfaction (Annamalai and Vasunandan 2024). On top of that, managers must also know the remuneration specifics and job conditions in their local labor market. They should use this data to inform HRM strategies and ensure alignment with employee expectations and market conditions.

Management must establish open and effective communication channels to capitalize on the powers of the Interior Communications (COM) element of IMO. Effective COM execution ensures that employees are fully informed about company policies, career promotions, changes, and achievements. Encouraging two-way communication will make employees feel comfortable voicing their concerns and suggestions, reducing gossiping and tension caused by feelings of uncertainty. In doing so, managers can capitalize on the benefits from the latest available technologies such as AI (Cuesta-Valiño et al. 2025). Furthermore, in implementing the third IMO's critical element of Management Strategies (STR), management must develop and execute comprehensive HRM strategies comprising clear career development paths, performance-based transparent rewards, new employee onboarding, and continuous T&D programs. In this domain, organizations should guarantee that these strategies are supported by top management for adequate commitment and resource allocation. According to our findings, implementing IMO with these specific strategies can make fulfilling business and social purposes plausible for the organization.

In extrapolating these discernments to different economic sectors, we assert that the findings are suitable for organisations operating predominantly in service industries, such as tourism and hospitality, HORECA (hotel-restaurant-café, which denotes the public dining and catering sector), retail, and corporate services. The obtained data have these sectors prominently represented in the research sample. Internal communications and management strategies are linked to service encounters, customer experience, and frontline performance in the servicescape, making IMO implementation especially impactful. Similarly, for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), where resources for eloquent HR systems may be scarce, focusing on the core pillars of IMO, comprising clear internal communication, informal feedback routines, and strategy transparency, can provide a low-cost yet effective pathway to improve employee satisfaction with their job and alignment with fulfilling the business and social purpose of their organisation. The recommendations above require their adaptation, bearing in mind the specifics of the particular sector where managers plan to apply them. Such a sector-savvy approach will help managers decipher our findings into practical, actionable strategies suited to varying organisational contexts to achieve success in business and social purpose fulfilment enacted by IMO.

Finally, the distinct research outcome pursuant to a link between social and business purpose fulfillment accentuates an alarm call for organizations to align their social and business purposes. Managers must acknowledge that fulfilling social purpose does not necessarily render the fulfillment of the organization's business purpose. Subsequently, managers should regularly monitor and critically evaluate the interplay between their social and business purposes to ensure their alignment,

prioritizing activities, policies, and strategies that facilitate the harmonious coexistence of these two kinds of a firm's purpose.

5.3 | Limitations and Future Research

The accomplished research has several limitations requiring attention from researchers planning studies in the same field. First, as this research has been the first attempt to explore the nexus of IMO with social and business purposes fulfillment, we applied a conventional, basic IMO model comprising working environment intelligence and interior communications, developing and executing responsive strategy constructs as suggested by S. P. Gounaris (2006). More recent studies (Ruizalba et al. 2014; Kazakov et al. 2021) have developed and validated more complex IMO frameworks comprising second and third-order latent constructs sculpting IMO implementation. With that being said, we chart a trajectory for future scholarly inquiries into this intersection by encouraging future researchers to employ these sophisticated models to explore the IMO concept in the context of social and business purpose fulfillment. These future insights will undoubtedly provide a more profound understanding of the linkage between these two studied conceptions.

Next, as noted previously, our research cannot evince positive effects arising from the linkage between social and business purposes fulfillment, adding to the ongoing debate in the literature on the interplay between these notions. Consequently, this debate urges and calls for the further examination of the noted relationships in future research endeavors. This particular revelation, unveiled by this study, prompts a reconsideration of established correlations between social and business purposes. As delineated earlier, our results align with corroborative findings from Hamdoun et al. (2021), further accentuating the intricate nature of the social/business purpose relationship, necessitating a more solid comprehension in academia. In this line, we recommend that future researchers consider the context-specific attributes that sway social purpose and its intricate interplay with business purpose imperatives.

In addition, as the present research relied on the data collected utilizing a cross-sectional design, we must acknowledge that causal inferences stemming from the obtained results should be interpreted cautiously, as asserted in Bollen and Pearl (2013). Although the PLS-SEM technique is a proven, robust technique allowing for testing directional paths based on theory and prior empirical research, we suggest that future fellow researchers employ experimental or, even better, longitudinal studies to substantiate causalities appearing in their respective frameworks more robustly.

Finally, this study has a limitation concerning an issue with the findings' generalisability due to data collection in research settings pertinent to one country, typical of Eastern Europe. In this respect, similarly to Goutam et al. (2021), we admit that the conclusions obtained may reflect region-specific socio-institutional specifics. To tackle the noted limitation, we urge future researchers to develop data collection methods encompassing various continents, markets, and business sectors. Such methodologies will provide a better understanding of IMO and

social/business purposes fulfillment and contribute to this particular research field.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

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